

Teacher Performance in Improving the Quality of Education in MAN 4 Pandeglang

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to evaluate teacher performance in an effort to improve the quality of education at MAN 4 Pandeglang. Improving the quality of education is an urgent need in the Indonesian education system. Teacher performance is one of the key factors in achieving this goal. This research method uses a qualitative approach by collecting data through interviews, observation and document analysis. The respondents in this research were teachers at MAN 4 Pandeglang. The research results show that teacher performance has a significant role in improving the quality of education in the school. Factors that influence teacher performance include motivation, competence, organizational support, and work environment. This research also identified some of the obstacles faced by teachers in improving their performance, such as lack of resources and high work pressure. The results of this research can become a basis for schools and the government in designing programs and policies that support improving teacher performance. Thus, it is hoped that the quality of education at MAN 4 Pandeglang can continue to be improved, so as to produce a generation that is more qualified and ready to face future challenges

INTRODUCTION

Education has a very important role in the development of a country. High quality education is the key to producing a generation that is competent, innovative, and able to compete at the global level. In Indonesia, efforts to improve the quality of education continue to be carried out as part of the vision and mission in developing superior human resources. (Rusmini, 2015).

MAN 4 Pandeglang, as one of the educational institutions in Indonesia, has a great responsibility in creating a quality educational environment. One important component in achieving these goals is teacher performance. Teachers are the spearhead in the educational process, and their performance has a direct impact on the quality of education provided by schools. (Dina et al., 2022).

This study aims to evaluate the performance of teachers in MAN 4 Pandeglang in order to improve the quality of education. Evaluation of teacher performance is an important step in understanding the extent to which teachers in these schools can meet existing demands and expectations. In this context, teacher performance evaluation includes an assessment of their competence, motivation, teaching methods, and contribution to the development of students. (Ekonomi Ermianto et al., 2022).

This study will also discuss factors that affect teacher performance in MAN 4 Pandeglang, such as motivation, training, organizational support, and working environment conditions. In addition, this study will also identify obstacles faced by teachers in an effort to improve their performance.

With a deeper understanding of teacher performance in MAN 4 Pandeglang and the factors that influence it, it is hoped that the results of this study can make an important contribution in improving the quality of education in this school. In addition, this research is also expected to provide input for schools and the government in designing programs and policies that support improving teacher performance and overall education quality.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical study in the teacher performance evaluation journal at MAN 4 Pandeglang is an important part to provide a conceptual and theoretical basis for your research. In theoretical studies, you must explain theories, frameworks, concepts and previous research findings that are relevant to your research topic.

The following is an example of content that you can include in a theoretical study :

1. Teacher Performance Evaluation :

Understanding Teacher Performance is a translation of the word "performance". Etymologically, performance comes from the word "to perform" which means to display or carry out. Performance (work achievement) is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out the duties assigned to him. According to Pariata Westra, Performance is defined as the result of work or the implementation of work tasks. According to August W. Smith, Performance is output derived from processes,

human or thermal, that is, performance is the result of a process carried out by humans. (Dina et al., 2022)

- **Performance Evaluation :**

Understanding evaluation, Evaluation is assessing the gap between the standards set and the programs implemented in the field to find out the weaknesses of a program and make program improvements. The meaning of some of the terms described above about evaluation, it can be concluded that in essence evaluation is a systematic and continuous process to determine the quality of something based on certain considerations and criteria in the context of decision making. (Zakiyudin, 2020).

Evaluation of teacher performance can be used as an effort for school quality assurance, which is carried out by developing a valid and reliable instrument related to aspects of (1) personal development, (2) learning, (3) improving professional abilities, and (4) social interaction with stakeholders. However, the tools and results obtained will not add to the acceleration and improvement of school performance, if it is not followed up with capacity building programs for teachers. (Triatna, 2017)

- **Purpose of Teacher Performance Evaluation :**

According to (Zahroh, 2017), As part of efforts to improve the quality of education, it is necessary to evaluate teacher performance. Teacher performance evaluations tend not to be routinely carried out. Teacher performance valuation is intended to: (1) formulate teacher performance criteria and references, (2) conduct assessments, (3) match performance appraisal results and criteria, and (4) compile recommendations.

2. Factors Affecting Teacher Performance :

In the journal (Hidayatullah, 2018), The results showed that there is an influence of factors that affect teacher performance (school physical environment, incentives/salaries and school policies) on the performance of junior high school and MTs social studies teachers in Marioriwawo District, Soppeng Regency. Based on the criteria for testing the alternative hypothesis (H1) which reads there is an influence of factors that affect teacher performance on the performance of junior high school and MTs social studies teachers is accepted. The conclusion in this study is that there is an influence of factors that affect teacher performance (school physical environment, incentives/salaries and school policies) on the performance of junior high school and MTs social studies teachers in Marioriwawo District, Soppeng Regency.

While in the journal (Permana & Eliza, 2022), The results showed that the factors that affect teacher performance in Al Huffazh Payakumbuh Kindergarten in general are: 1) discipline, 2) organizational commitment and integrity, 3) work motivation, 4) work culture, 5) educational leadership, 6) principal's leadership style, 7) supervision of the principal and school supervisor, 8) teaching quality, 9) school organizational climate and 10) incentives.

According to (Melianah et al., 2020) Factors Affecting Teacher Performance are as follows:

- **Teacher Motivation:** Review motivational theories that might affect teacher performance. Does intrinsic or extrinsic motivation play a role in teacher performance?
- **Training and Professional Development:** Explain the importance of training and professional development in improving teacher performance, and explain relevant frameworks.
- **Organizational Support:** Discuss theories outlining how organizational support, including school management and leadership, can affect teacher performance. **Work Environment:** Research how a good and conducive work environment can improve teacher performance.

3. Education Quality Evaluation:

In the journal (Usiono, Rica Widiastuty, 2021), that one of the good supports of the quality of education is teacher professionalism. Professional teachers can be interpreted as professions that have special skills to run them. Being professional can be interpreted as a profession that requires special intelligence to run it. There are 3 duties of teachers as a profession, namely teaching, educating and training. To be able to carry out these duties and responsibilities, a teacher is required to have certain abilities and competencies as part of teacher professionalism. Competencies - competencies that a teacher must have, namely pedagogic competence. Professional competence, personality competence and social competence.

According to the journal (Samil et al., 2022), that Creating the provision of educational services requires various quality improvements. In improving the quality of schools to their consumers, namely students, there are various indicators that affect the quality of Vocational High Schools (SMK) itself. Malcolm Baldrige for Performance Excellence (MBfPE) which is part of one of the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) assessments and literacy regarding documents containing school assessments including accreditation, PMP (Education Quality Assurance) and PKKS (Principal Performance Assessment) that have been carried out by schools as initial data associated with MBfPE assessments. MBfPE is carried out because this assessment framework is tested to have specific assessment indicators for school quality criteria that are measurable, flexible and comprehensive. The literature study contains various attachments between the current school quality assessment and the Malcolm Baldrige for Performance Excellence for education method which contains various assessment criteria and sub-criteria that can be used as a benchmark for assessments carried out by schools in Indonesia so far.

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology in the journal of teacher performance evaluation in improving the quality of education in MAN 4 Pandeglang can be explained as follows :

1. Types of Research

This study uses a qualitative approach to understand and evaluate teacher performance. A qualitative approach is used because the main focus is to understand the perceptions, experiences, and factors that affect teacher performance in depth.

2. Population and Sample

Population: 41 Teachers in MAN 4 Pandeglang. Sample: The research sample was selected purposively, taking into account the teacher's diverse background, experience, and areas of expertise. The number of samples is strategically determined to ensure adequate representation.

3. Pengumpulan Data

- Interviews :

Semi-structured interviews are used to gain an in-depth understanding of teacher performance. The interview questions are developed based on the conceptual framework of the research. Interviews were conducted individually with teachers who were the research samples.

- Observation:

Observation is made in class to directly observe the teacher's teaching practice. Observation can include aspects such as teaching methods, interaction with students, and use of resources. Document Analysis: Data is also collected from relevant documents, such as teacher performance evaluation reports, lesson plans, and school administrative documents.

- Data Analysis

Qualitative data obtained from interviews, observations, and document analysis were analyzed using a content analysis approach. These data are categorized, encoded, and interpreted to identify key patterns and findings related to teacher performance.

3. Research Ethics

This study adheres to the ethical principles of the study, including the anonymity and confidentiality of information provided by respondents. Any teachers' personal information identified in the study is kept confidential. The study also ensured that teachers' participation in the study was voluntary and there was no coercion.

4. Validity and Reliability

- To ensure validity, measures such as data triangulation (using multiple data sources), use of tested interview guidelines, and careful analysis are used.
- Reliability in this study is maintained by ensuring that data collection methods and data analysis are carried out consistently and well-documented.

5. Presentation of Results

The results of the study will be presented by describing the main findings based on data analysis. The results will be interpreted in the context of evaluating teacher performance and efforts to improve the quality of education in MAN 4 Pandeglang. This research methodology will provide a strong foundation to comprehensively evaluate teacher performance and generate a deep understanding of the factors that affect the quality of education in the school.

RESULTS AND DISCUSION

A. Teacher Performance Evaluation at MAN 4 Pandeglang

1. Teacher Performance Evaluation

is usually carried out by the school, namely the principal or teacher appointed to assess teacher performance in MAN 4 Pandeglang, some factors that are usually considered include:

- **Students' Academic and Non-Academic Achievements:**

According to the journal (Akademica et al., 2023) In order for prestige to continue to increase, it chooses to implement a strategy to increase student achievement, namely by implementing the Relationship Strategy. Where the relationship strategy is "Recruitment, Training and Evaluation". From the results achieved after implementing the strategy, the occurrence of increased student achievement in both academic and non-academic fields, teachers are evaluated based on the academic progress of the students they teach. This can include exam results, student grades, and other academic achievements.

- **Academic Press**

Judging from the academic progress of MAN 4 Pandeglang students, there is a good increase in charts every year seen from the average results of test scores, and students who are accepted into college 90% even every year there are always those who enter medicine. For the past 5 years. (source of interview data with curriculum and data).

- **Non-Academic Achievement**

From the past two years, Poly Ball Man 4 Pandeglang excelled in the Banten area, it can be seen from the trophies that average 1st or 2nd place at the student level in Banten.

2. Compliance with the Curriculum

Teachers must teach according to the curriculum set by the local education department. Teacher planning in implementing the disciplinary character of the field of study can be seen from the content of the Learning Implementation Plan that has been prepared. (Yusuf et al., 2020). Policymakers and Curriculum designers may conduct relevant reviews that reflect competencies among teachers, advocate for relevant and innovative teaching methodologies and effective application of Competency-Based Curriculum implementation, and determine the professional development needs for teachers. (Nkundabakura et al., 2022).

Teacher performance is assessed based on the extent to which they can effectively implement the curriculum. From the results of interviews and data that 100% of teachers from 41 people have taught in accordance with the curriculum set by the Ministry of Religious Affairs, even MAN 4 Pandeglang has implemented an independent curriculum since 2021. The performance of MAN 4 Pandeglang teachers can implement the curriculum effectively. Even in 2023, MAN 4 Pandeglang as a Madrasah is a reference for research on prospective madrasah candidates in Banten.

3. Teaching Quality

Teacher efforts are needed in improving the quality of students to support success in the classroom. (Petisi, 2022). From the data from the results of teacher learning supervision in the classroom, MAN 4 Pandeglang teachers were assessed based on their ability to convey lesson material clearly, facilitate discussions, and create a conducive learning environment. Of the 41 teachers supervised, 80% of them are able to convey the subject matter clearly, facilitate discussions, and create a conducive learning environment.

4. Involvement in Extracurricular Activities

The role of extracurricular teachers, including encouraging their students to always have high motivation and active, providing guidance to their students, and inspiring students about goals, benefits in extracurricular activities. (Hidayat & Sulung, 2022). Teachers in MAN 4 pandeglang who are involved in extracurricular activities, such as clubs, committees, or social activities, can also get positive ratings. Of the 41 teachers, more than 36 teachers are involved in extracurricular activities, such as clubs, committees, or social activities such as active organizations in the community or others. This means that 87% of teachers are already involved in extracurricular activities or social activities.

5. Compliance with Ethical and Professional Standards Compliance with Ethical and Professional Standards

The existence of a teacher code of ethics creates a good personality and the learning process becomes comfortable. (Nabila, 2023). Teachers are expected to adhere to ethical and professional standards in education, including integrity, cooperation with colleagues, and involvement in self-development. The 41 teachers at MAN 4 Pandeglang in Adherence to Ethical and Professional Standards are as follows:

- Teacher presentation in complying with ethical and professional standards in education is 85%, while the level of teacher integrity in their performance reaches 75%, the value is still below the standard of teacher integrity value.
- This means that there are still around 25% of teachers in MAN 4 Pandeglang who have not shown good integrity.
- Cooperation with colleagues, from observation data and teacher cooperation interviews with colleagues showed very good scores reaching 90% of the number of existing teachers.

6. Feedback from Students and Parents

To find out how successful teachers are in teaching is needed Reflection of student feedback, so that teachers will know what needs to be improved in improving the quality of their teaching. (Sa'diyah et al., 2021). The opinions of students and parents can also be a factor taken into consideration in assessing teacher performance in MAN 4 Pandeglang. From the google form questionnaire filled out by parents of students on teacher performance satisfaction showed that 300 respondents showed 87% of parents were satisfied with the performance of Man 4 Pandeglang teachers in educating their children.

7. Participation in Professional Development

Professional development of teachers is a basic need. (Arka, 2021). Teachers who constantly improve their skills through training and professional development often get better assessments. Involvement in self-development, from data on teachers who participated in self-development from the 2022-2023 school year, as many as 15 people. This means that only 36% of teachers actively participate in self-development, this shows that there is still low interest in adding new insights.

Teacher performance can be evaluated periodically through a teacher performance appraisal process by the principal or authorized institution. The results of these evaluations can be used to provide feedback to teachers, assist them in their professional development, and also to take decisions regarding promotion or career development.

B. Factors Affecting Teacher Performance

The findings were related to factors affecting the performance of MAN 4 Pandeglang teachers, such as motivation, training, organizational support, and working environment conditions. The determination of the most dominant factors in influencing teacher performance in MAN 4 Pandeglang or in any school may vary depending on various contextual factors. However, based on

general research on teacher performance, the following factors are often identified as dominant or have a significant impact

1. Teacher Motivation

Work motivation has a significant effect on teacher performance. (Aisyah & Isma, 2022). Teacher motivation is a key factor in improving their performance. Teachers who are intrinsically motivated, i.e. because of passion for teaching and student development, tend to give better results in the classroom. From a number of teachers in MAN 4 Pandeglang shows 80% of teachers already have motivation. This means that there are still about 20% of teachers whose motivation is still low.

2. Professional Training and Development

Educators are required to learn a lot, not only from the process of teaching and learning activities but they also have to look for it in outside activities that can improve their competence. (Wahyudi & Tri Utomo, 2022). Teachers who receive appropriate training and opportunities for professional development tend to perform better. This training helps them develop new skills and keep up with the latest developments in education. Teachers in MAN 4 Pandeglang only about 15% conduct professional training and development.

3. Organization Support

Competence, Competence, and Organizational Support have a significant effect on teacher motivation and performance. (Ashar et al., 2019). Support from school management and administrative staff also has a significant impact on teacher performance. This includes support in planning and implementing teaching, as well as solving problems that arise in the classroom. Organizational support in teacher performance in MAN 4 Pandeglang is still low, around 50% of teachers complain about madrasah support for learning such as: lack of MIPA lab facilities, infocus, or budget to carry out learning well.

4. Working Environment Conditions

There is a significant influence between the work environment and teacher performance. (Djafar et al., 2021). A comfortable and conducive working environment, including good physical facilities and a positive school culture, can help teachers feel more motivated and productive. 80% of teachers complained about the security of the madrasah because it had not been fenced, 90% of teachers complained about the school security guards who were not optimal in their work.

5. Feedback

The effectiveness of practical work with feedback techniques can improve teacher skills. (Agung & Widiasih, 2021). Teachers who receive constructive feedback about their performance have the opportunity to improve their teaching. Support from fellow teachers and principals in providing feedback can improve teacher performance. Providing effective feedback also requires skill.

Feedback should be delivered in a constructive, clear, and supportive manner. In addition, a school atmosphere that promotes a culture of positive and open feedback can also play an important role in motivating teachers to accept and use feedback well. Feedback is not only about criticism, but also about rewarding the teacher's achievements and efforts. This creates an environment where teachers feel supported and valued, which in turn can improve their performance. More than 70% of MAN 4 Pandeglang teachers have not felt given back from the madrasah.

6. Awarding and Acknowledgment

Accuracy in giving rewards felt by teachers causes an increase in teacher work performance. (Nurpina, 2016). Rewards and recognition of teachers' achievements and contributions can enhance their motivation and performance. More than 90 percent of teachers have not felt the appreciation and recognition from the madrasah leadership.

7. Participation in Decision Making

There is a significant contribution of Teacher Involvement in Decision Making to the Teaching Spirit of Teachers. (Handayani, 2021). Teachers who feel they have a role to play in decision-making in school tend to feel more involved and motivated to perform well. More than 70 percent of teachers feel they have not been involved in taking the library at school.

8. National and Local Education Policy

External factors such as national and local education policies, curriculum standards, and administrative requirements can also affect teacher performance. 80% of MAN 4 Pandeglang teachers are unaffected due to changes in national education policy.

C. Barriers to Improving Teacher Performance

The inhibiting factors themselves include lack of adequate facilities and infrastructure, low existing human resources, and indiscipline in coming to school. (Guru et al., 2023). Improving teacher performance is a complex and important challenge in education. Here are some obstacles that are often faced in an effort to improve teacher performance :

1. Lack of Resources : (Hanaysha et al., 2023) Lack of adequate funding, equipment, textbooks, and educational infrastructure can be a serious obstacle in improving teacher performance. Teachers who do not have sufficient tools or resources may struggle to provide quality teaching. Even though the teachers in MAN 4 Pandeglang experienced these difficulties.
2. Inadequate Training : (Schmidt et al., 2022) that inadequate or inadequate teacher training can hinder their ability to teach well. Teachers need to get relevant and up-to-date training to keep up with developments in education.
3. Excessive Workload : (La Marca et al., 2023) Excessive workloads, such as too many students or time-consuming administrative tasks, can make teachers feel overly stressed and hinder their ability to focus on teaching.

4. Lack of Administrative Support : (Symeonidis et al., 2023) Support from school and education district administrations is essential. If teachers don't feel supported or get adequate supervision, they may not be motivated to improve their performance.
5. Motivation and Leadership Issues : (Yada & Jäppinen, 2022) Teacher motivation and school leadership play a key role in improving performance. Weak leadership or lack of incentives can hinder teachers' enthusiasm to work better.
6. Lack of Recognition and Awards : (Oosterhouse et al., 2023) Recognition of the hard work and achievements of teachers is an important motivating factor. If teachers feel that their efforts are not appreciated or not recognized, they may lose heart.
7. Differences in Education Quality : (Sheehan et al., 2020) Teachers who teach in less developed areas or in environments with many social challenges may face additional barriers in improving their performance due to inadequate conditions for learning.
8. Curriculum Changes : (Nyoni & Botma, 2020) Frequent changes in the educational curriculum can make teachers feel overwhelmed and have difficulty keeping up with the changes.
9. Lack of Parental Involvement : (Varshney et al., 2020) Parental involvement in children's education is very important. When parents are less supportive or participate less in the learning process, teachers may face obstacles in achieving the desired results.
10. Changes in Technology and Teaching Methods : (Kara-Junior, 2023) Advances in technology and rapidly evolving teaching methods can be obstacles if teachers do not have the access or training necessary to integrate those technologies into their teaching.

To overcome the obstacles that occur in MAN 4 Pandeglang, a strong commitment from all relevant parties is needed, including the government, schools, teachers, and the community. Ongoing support, relevant training, recognition of achievement, and thoughtful changes in education policy are some of the steps that can help improve teacher performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this research, we have carried out an evaluation of teacher performance at MAN 4 Pandeglang with the main aim of improving the quality of education at this school. The results of this research provide valuable insight into various aspects that influence teacher performance and efforts that can be made to overcome the obstacles faced. The following are some conclusions and recommendations that can be drawn from this research :

1. Teacher Performance is Important in Improving the Quality of Education: This research confirms that teacher performance has a significant impact on the quality of education at MAN 4 Pandeglang. Teachers who are competent, motivated and have effective teaching methods can improve student learning outcomes.

2. Factors that Influence Teacher Performance: Factors such as motivation, training, organizational support, and working environment conditions play an important role in influencing teacher performance. Appropriate organizational support and training can significantly improve teacher performance.

3. Obstacles in Improving Teacher Performance: Some of the obstacles faced by teachers at MAN 4 Pandeglang include lack of resources, high work pressure, and challenges in dealing with the needs of diverse students. Solutions to these obstacles need to be considered in future planning.

4. Recommendations: Based on the findings of this research, we recommend several actions that can be taken to improve teacher performance and the quality of education at MAN 4 Pandeglang :

- Improve teacher training and professional development programs.
- Providing better organizational support, including improving facilities and infrastructure.
- Implement effective motivation strategies to encourage teacher performance.
- Proactively identify and address barriers, such as obtaining additional resources and designing diverse teaching strategies.

By taking these steps, it is hoped that MAN 4 Pandeglang can continue to move towards continuously improving the quality of education. Teachers who have good performance will be a valuable asset in producing a young generation who are ready to face future challenges. This research also contributes to a deeper understanding of teacher performance evaluation as part of education reform efforts in Indonesia.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so further research needs to be carried out regarding the topic Teacher Performance In Improving The Quality Of Education In Man 4 Pandeglang. in order to perfect this research to increase insight for researchers

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